

DISCRETE DAMAGE MODELLING OF COUNTERSUNK FASTENED LAMINATED COMPOSITES IN BEARING

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ABSTRACT

Modern airframes fabricated from composite materials seek to minimize the Outer-Mould-Line (OML) disturbance for enhanced aerodynamic performance and so bolted lap joints with countersunk fasteners are typically used. Strength and durability prediction of these structures is challenging because of complexity in accounting for the interaction of various modes of damage. To enhance sustainment and permit less conservative design more accurate strength and durability predictions are sought. The current study entailed experimental testing of countersunk fastened joints typical of advanced fighter aircraft construction loaded in tension and bearing. Micro-computed X-ray tomography was utilized to observe the development of damage and optical photography used to observe final failure. Strength predictions of failure were conducted using physics-based methods including Discrete Damage Modelling (DDM) and Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM). The experimental results showed that sub-critical fibre compression failures occurred near the bearing face of the fastener in both joining laminates at approximately 60% of the final failure load. The sub-critical fibre failures led to reductions in joint stiffness, accelerated fastener rotation and eventual failure of the joint. The work continues to build a foundation for physics-based composites strength and, potentially, durability prediction that can be used for improved sustainment of aircraft.

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern airframes fabricated from composite materials seek to minimize the Outer-Mould-Line (OML) disturbance for enhanced aerodynamic performance. This poses a challenge for highly loaded joints used in design to connect assemblies and also for repair. Typically, bolted lap joints with countersunk fasteners are used. Strength prediction in general for composite materials is a significant challenge because of complexity in accounting for the interaction of various modes of damage. This includes matrix cracking, delamination and fiber failure, which cooperatively lead to the loss of the load carrying capacity and/or loss of integrity. The challenge extends further for countersunk fastened connections, which is complicated by the interaction with the fastener and tapering within the fastener hole [1–4]. Recent studies have shown the feasibility of using Discrete Damage Modelling (DDM) to accurately predict the tensile and compression failure of notched composites and proposed a method for predicting the static bearing failure of joints with through-holes [4]. Other studies using DDM showed how taper within the notch requires special attention to achieve accuracy in prediction [5,6]. In addition, the final failure of the composite laminate in tension appears to be best predicted using Critical Failure Volume (CFV) statistical criteria [6] that accounts for the “size effects” [6–8]. Continuum Damage Mechanics, however, is recommended for representation of fibre damage development to accurately predict compression failure [4]. The current work utilized CFV to check for fibre failure in tension and CDM to account for progressive fibre failure in compression. DDM is gaining traction as the preferred method for accurately simulating composite failure [9]. It attempts to model each mode of physical failure in a composite laminate, their interaction during sub-

critical damage development and ultimate failure, applicable for simulation of the process in which cracks or splits observed experimentally evolve into delaminations. There are several DDM methods that are proposed and each was founded upon the original extended finite element method (X-FEM) proposed by Moes [10]. In these methods, the displacement discontinuity introduced via ply splitting (or cracking) is modelled discretely by adding degrees of freedom to the element and approximate its effect on the kinematics of the model. Hence, by so doing, cracking and in some cases delamination is permitted without requiring re-meshing. One such approach is the Regularized extended finite element method (Rx-FEM) proposed by Iarve [11], where the Heaviside step function associated with the crack surface is replaced with a continuous function. In so doing, the Gauss integration schema for the computation of the element stiffness matrix is preserved. The technique also offers the potential to provide high-fidelity numerical insight into the onset and initiation of damage.

The objective of the current work was to examine the suitability of DDM for the prediction of bearing failure of composite laminates with a countersunk fastener. The single lap joint configuration shown in Figure 1 was chosen for examination using the test method ASTM 5961 [12]. X-ray micro-computed tomography was utilized to characterize the morphology of matrix damage development via interrupted testing. In addition to the global response, the observed damage was used to further examine the validity of the models. Attempts were made to ensure the input properties were based on lower level lamina tests only and thus in-principle satisfy the requirements of a blind prediction. The results confirmed that it was possible to use DDM in combination with CDM to predict the static bearing response of a countersunk fastened laminate. The analyses of the countersunk fastener, however, needed to deviate from the method used for the through hole in Reference [4]. Specifically, convergence problems prevented an interface definition between the laminates and contact pairing. Therefore, a clamping force could not be applied through the joint as part of the analysis. In the meantime, a bounding study was conducted that considered a case of perfect clamping (Analysis A) and a case where the clamping force was minimal (Analysis B). That is, the effect of minimal clamping was first considered that included DDM for matrix and CDM for fibre damage development. Perfect clamp-up was considered via an identical model except that matrix damage development was precluded. The precise cause for the convergence problems are currently being investigated and additional models are in development as clearly clamping force, contact pairing and frictional effects between the laminates significantly affects the results.

Figure 1 Single shear bearing specimen tested in accordance with ASTM 5961 (a) enclosed within fixture, (b) assembled including mounts for extensometer and (c) exploded view.

2 TEST SETUP

The specimens were fabricated with Cytec IM7/5250-4 carbon/bismaelimide (BMI) pre prep with a nominal ply thickness of 0.125 mm. The stacking sequence is referred to as stiff orthotropic

[45/0/0/-45/90]_{3s}, with a higher percentage of 0° plies in the loading direction than in the off axis directions. The nominal 30 ply laminate thickness was 3.75 mm, which was close to the actual thickness. The laminates were cured initially in an autoclave at 177°C for 6 hours at 586 kPa, then post cured at 227°C for a further 6 hours. The specimens were machined using a three axis MultiCAM computer numeric controlled (CNC) router (Model S2418, Australia) [17]. The specimen geometry and toolpath was generated using the computer aided design (CAD)/computer aided manufacturing (CAM) software suite, Siemens NX Version 10 [18]. A 3 mm diameter carbide burr cutter was used for machining with a tool rotational speed of 10000 rpm and a maximum step over length of 0.1 mm. The specimen edges were machined using a 6 mm diameter tool. The specimens were tested under displacement control on an MTS 100 kN load capacity test machine (MTS Landmark, USA) with a loading rate selected (0.5 mm/minute) to achieve a specimen failure within 30 minutes. A total of 10 specimens were tested to failure during the program. Three additional specimens tested to differing loads to permit observation of sub-critical damage development using X-ray micro-computed tomography. A single specimen of each size was examined by X-ray micro computed tomography (micro CT) scanning using an Xylon Precision Versa (Xylon Precision, Germany) CT scanner to study the damage state post-failure. Several scans were performed at various resolutions ranging from 10 to 30 micron voxel size with a 70 kV, 6 W microfocus X-ray source.

3 MESH INDEPENDENT MODELLING

The discrete damage modelling approach consists of mesh-independent modeling of matrix cracks in each ply of the laminate, and modeling the delamination between the plies by using a cohesive formulation at the ply interface. The simulation begins without any initial matrix cracks, which then are inserted based on a failure criterion during the simulation. In the present paper, we utilize the LaRC04 failure criteria [13], which includes failure criterion based on physical models of each failure mode. That is, matrix cracks are inserted if matrix failure criterion with LaRC04 is exceeded. The matrix cracks are modeled by using the regularized mesh-independent cracking (MIC) formulation [11,14]. This formulation is a derivative of the x-FEM proposed in [10], where the cracked element is enriched by additional degrees of freedom to ensure the displacement jump. These additional degrees of freedom are associated with the shape functions, which are essentially partitioned along the crack surface, and represented by the Heaviside step function. In approach incorporated within the BSAM code [11,14], the step function is approximated by the same shape functions as the displacements. A critical aspect of the regularized formulation is the constitutive behavior in the gradient zone. The approach taken below directly incorporates the surface discontinuity-based cohesive law developed by Turon et al. [15] in the formulation of the fracture energy of the gradient zone. The damage parameter controls the crack opening, and will be used below to display the length of the cracks. The same cohesive law is also used to model the delaminations between plies. Mathematical details of the formulation are described elsewhere [11,14], and will be omitted here. A general flow of the solution process is given in Figure 2. At the core of the solution is a non-linear Newton–Raphson (NR) solution loop, which equilibrates the displacement field at a given load level by iteratively finding the distribution of the damage variable d in all integration points. After the convergence criterion is met, the stress field is examined in each integration point by using the LaRC04 failure criterion and, if the matrix criterion is exceeded, the enrichment degrees of freedom required to model a new MIC are added to the solution. In this case, we perform the NR loop process to re-equilibrate the solution without adding the load increment. The stress field is then checked again, and if the failure criterion is still exceeded at any point, a new MIC is added. In the case when no more MICs are added, the load is increased, and the process repeated. Fiber failure criterion, Critical Failure Volume (CFV) [8,16] and CDM [17] is typically used to stop the computation if fiber macro-failure in tension is detected or locally soften if compression failure is predicted. For this study, both techniques were utilized.

Figure 2 Flow chart of the automated mesh independent crack (MIC) insertion and growth procedure

The finite element models were analysed with the Rx-FEM method implemented in the proprietary solution code, BSAM. The models were loaded in tension via an applied displacement at one end and fixed at the other. The specimen is gripped close to the termination of the fixture during testing. Therefore, the model length was set to 346 mm, which is the length of the fixture. The boundary conditions, which also included out-of-plane constraints to account for the fixture, are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Finite element model boundary conditions

The mesh comprised hexagonal solid elements of which the edge length of the finest element was 0.05 mm. Each ply was modelled with a single element through the thickness and attached to its neighbouring ply via cohesive elements. At the joint, strong cohesive connections were included on the bearing faces between the fastener and the composite. Cohesive connections were not specified on faces that were not in bearing and therefore permitted separation in these areas. The connection sets between the fastener and the composite are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Fastener connection sets

For these analyses, excessive run times were encountered when attempting to model the interface between the joining laminates which could not be resolved easily. This also precluded the application of clamp-up pressure using the method detailed in Reference [4]. To permit an investigation, two analyses were conducted that ignored interface friction between the laminates. Analysis A assumed all matrix damage mechanisms were suppressed and approximated perfect clamp-up conditions. Analysis B permitted the development of matrix damage, but since clamp-up pressure was ignored, approximated the conditions of a “loose” fastener. A more representative analysis that includes the effects of clamping and laminate to laminate sliding is planned for the future, once the root cause of convergence problems have been identified and a modelling strategy developed.

4 RESULTS

Mechanical response and failure modes

With reference to both the load versus crosshead displacement and bearing stress versus bearing strain curves Figure 5, the mechanical response is linear up to 60-70% of the failure load, and then non-linear to failure. In addition, a BSAM analysis was performed with and without the presence of discrete damage to the matrix, and ignoring the effects of clamping. The results from the analyses matched the experimental results reasonably closely in the linear region. The analyses results effectively bounded the experimental results in the non-linear region. That is, when discrete damage in the matrix was suppressed and only CDM damage to the fibres considered, the joint stiffness was observed to reduce, but not at the rate observed experimentally. When discrete damage to the matrix was permitted (Analysis B), the joint stiffness and overall strength was observed to reduce significantly, much more than that observed experimentally. That is, the results appear to confirm previously known conclusions from other bearing analyses [6] of composites that the clamping force suppresses the development of matrix damage significantly.

Figure 5 (a) Load versus crosshead and (b) bearing stress versus bearing strain

With reference to Figure 6, typically the final failure observed experimentally occurred when the fastener shank failed around the location of the nut. Significant composite damage was observed post-failure within both adherends. Overall, the coefficient of variation (CV) in the measured strength results was 8%, which was considered relatively good considering the complexity of manufacture and extent of sub-critical damage prior to final failure.

Figure 6 Typical final failure showing significant pin rotation, damage to the composite near the fastener head and eventual failure of the bolt on the nut side

Stress concentration

With reference to Figure 7, the axial strain predicted in joints with (Figure 7a) and without (Figure 7b) fibre damage confirmed that adjacent to the bearing face, a significant compressive stress concentration was induced. Almost equivalent in magnitude, however, was the presence of a high tensile stress in regions where the load bearing (0°) fibres run tangentially to the hole. Throughout the simulations, however, only compressive failure was predicted as the lamina tensile strength in the fibre direction (X_t) was approximately 60% higher than the compressive strength (X_c). Where compressive damage was observed (Figure 7b), the region of compressive stress was predicted to enlarge. In the case where matrix damage was suppressed (Analysis A), the laminate continued to support an

increasing load until overload of the fastener was predicted. The same progression to failure was observed in experiments. In the case where matrix damage was permitted to evolve (Analysis B), matrix cracks initiated from peak tensile stress areas until a shear-out failure was predicted. This progression to failure was not observed in any of the experiments and thus appears that this morphology was inhibited in practice by clamping forces not included in Analysis B.

Note: Fastener not shown to permit observation of stress concentrations on the countersunk bearing face

Figure 7 Longitudinal strain (ϵ_{xx}) as viewed from the countersunk head side (fastener and bottom laminate not shown) for (a) $P = 12.2 \text{ kN}$ and (b) $P = 18.9 \text{ kN}$ (matrix damage suppressed)

Damage development and simulation

Further examination via interrupted testing and X-ray micro-CT was conducted to observe sub-critical composite damage mechanisms. Given the consistency of the final failure mode, the similarity of mechanical response and relatively low CV in measured strength, the results from the X-ray micro-CT may be considered typical of other specimens in the set. The X-ray micro-CT was specifically focussed around observing the condition of the composite just following the presence of non-linearity in the mechanical response (60-70% of failure load). Relatively coarse scans with a resolution of $30 \mu\text{m}$ were conducted to permit a field of view that encompassed the entire bearing region around the hole. With reference to Figure 8, the area of inquiry was limited to the laminate with the countersink (L2). Preliminary analysis showed this to be the area of highest stress concentration (Figure 7), and clear damage to the laminate (bulging) was observed in this area post-failure (Figure 8).

Note: Each laminate (L1 and L2) comprises 30 plies with stacking sequence $[45/0/0/-45/90]_{3s}$

Figure 8 Joint nomenclature

With reference to Figure 9, the X-ray micro-CT reconstruction, which was taken following an interruption to the test at approximately 60% failure load, and was sliced at various levels through the thickness to highlight observations of damage in plies of interest. In Figure 9, the coarse scan shows that sub-critical damage was only observed close to the bearing face of the joint which was an area

subjected to a high compressive stress concentration. Close examination of load bearing plies (0°) revealed fibre failures which were most extensive in plies closer to the bottom of laminate L2 (plies 32/33 and 37/38). Also, micro-buckling was clearly evident (Figure 9a inset), which further supported the contention that the sub-critical damage was due to compressive overload. No evidence of sub-critical fibre failures were observed in plies between the countersunk knee location and the top surface (I.e. plies 42/43 to 60).

Figure 9 Damage observed with X-ray micro-CT in (a) 0° ply group 32/33 (close to bottom), (b) 0° ply group 37/38 (close to countersink “knee” and (c) 0° ply group 42/43 (above countersink “knee”) of laminate L2

With reference to Figure 10, the predicted development of damage in the composite joint adherends was quite different when matrix damage development was suppressed. That is, it was previously shown that the predicted overall mechanical response in the non-linear region utilising Analysis A (matrix damage suppressed) was quite different to Analysis B (matrix damage permitted). The root

cause of this discrepancy is borne out of observations of the predicted sub-critical damage development shown in Figure 10. The predicted damage development using Analysis A matches reasonably closely the pattern of damage observed experimentally. Using Analysis B, matrix damage in the form of ply splitting was predicted to start from around 30% of the experimentally measured failure load. The splits coalesced into a “shear-out” type failure mode causing a significant reduction in joint stiffness. At around 50% of the experimentally measured failure load, delamination and progressive fibre damage modes were predicted that reduced the stiffness of the joint further and eventually caused a load drop. The splitting and delamination predicted using Analysis B was not observed experimentally but may explain why the full extent of joint stiffness reduction was not captured using Analysis A. It is believed that better predictions will be possible once an effective method for introducing a clamping force have been developed. As discussed previously, initial attempts to introduce the clamping force using a similar method to Reference [4] did not converge. Work is ongoing to determine the cause of the problem and develop improved models of the joint.

Figure 10 Predicted damage developed during loading of the countersunk single lap joint

5 DISCUSSION

The bearing strength of composite to composite single lap joint with a countersunk fastener was examined. The bearing performance of these joints is crucial as they are commonly used in the joining of structures on advanced fighter aircraft. The performance of the joints was measured experimentally and advanced experimental techniques such as micro-CT were used to accurately observe the development of sub-critical damage. The development of sub-critical damage in the form of both fibre and matrix mechanisms appears to cause a substantial joint stiffness reduction prior to final failure. In this study, Rx-FEM DDM was evaluated to determine if an accurate model that relied only on lamina input properties could be developed to predict the joint mechanical response to failure. Previous bearing studies considered only a through-hole, but provided suggested strategies for modelling the countersunk fastened joint considered herein.

This paper provides a good set of experimental data that confirms the presence of sub-critical fibre failure that appears to have a significant impact on the overall mechanical performance of the joint. Initial attempts with Rx-FEM, however, to accurately model the joint conditions including clamp-up were unsuccessful. That is, the models did not converge. It was speculated that this was due to significantly greater joint rotation and deflections for this single fastener case as opposed to previous

studies with multiple fasteners. In efforts to establish solutions that would converge, two models were developed that are reported herein. Neither solution considers clamp-up directly. The first (Analysis A) suppressed sub-critical matrix damage completely and effectively represents that case where there is perfect clamping. It was found that for this case the evolution of sub-critical fibre damage closely matched experimental observations with micro-CT. The amount of joint stiffness degradation, however, was significantly less than the experimentally measured response. The second (Analysis B) considered the development of both sub-critical matrix and fibre damage mechanisms. Since clamping force was ignored, this case represents the situation where the fastener is loose fitting. It was found that substantial matrix damage in the form of ply splitting was predicted at a relatively low load which eventually resulted in a predicted joint stiffness degradation that was much greater than the measured response. Also, the final failure load, as defined when the joint stiffness was consistently negative and/or a significant load drop occurred, was much lower as well. This confirms previously reported studies that highlighted the importance of considering the effect of clamp-up when predicting the bearing strength of mechanically fastened joints [4]. It may also explain why the joint stiffness degradation was under-predicted when sub-critical matrix damage development was ignored (Analysis A). Further studies are ongoing to develop improved models using Rx-FEM and other techniques that predict more accurately the single lap joint stiffness degradation, sub-critical composite damage development and final failure for aircraft sustainment applications.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The countersunk fastened joint is commonly used in the assembly of composite structures on advanced fighter aircraft. The bearing strength, and in particular the evolution of sub-critical damage, joint stiffness retention and final failure was examined experimentally and via numerical analysis using the Air Force Research Laboratory finite element software code, BSAM [14,20,21]. It was shown experimentally that sub-critical damage evolved at approximately 60% of the final failure load and progressively reduced the joint bearing stiffness until final failure. Final failure was typically via fastener overload in tension as a result of excessive rotation as the joint bearing stiffness progressively reduced.

X-ray micro-CT observations of critical regions of the joint following interrupted testing showed that sub-critical composite damage coinciding with the onset of non-linearity in the bearing response was predominantly fibre fracture. The locus of the sub-critical damage observed was confined to plies close to the interface between the joining adherends. Close observation of the sub-critical fibre fractures revealed micro-buckling, indicating compressive overload. Analyses confirmed that the failures occurred in regions of highest compressive stress concentration.

High fidelity finite element analysis using BSAM was conducted to determine if accurate bearing response predictions were possible based solely on lamina level input retrievable via standard test methods. In particular, it was sought to predict the non-linear response that was shown experimentally to be due to the onset of sub-critical composite damage. Initial modelling efforts using methods described in Reference [4] were unsuccessful due to convergence problems. The extent of joint rotation and deformation as the single fastened joint used herein appears to be much greater than for the multi-fastened joint considered in Reference [4]. Therefore, the joint considered herein appears to pose a greater challenge for progressive damage modelling than previously attempted.

As a step toward more accurate modelling of the joint, two models were developed and the results presented herein. Neither model accounted for the clamping force directly. Both models, however, were able to predict the bearing response in the linear region accurately. Analysis A represented the case of perfect clamping via suppression of the development of all sub-critical matrix damage. Only fibre fracture was permitted in both tension and compression and its effect was modelled using Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) [17]. The development of sub-critical fibre fracture in compression predicted using Analysis A matched the experimental observations reasonably closely. Analysis A, however, over-predicted the overall bearing stiffness in the presence of sub-critical damage. The second model, Analysis B, permitted the development of sub-critical matrix damage via Discrete Damage Modelling (DDM) [11], as well as, progressive fibre fracture using CDM and represented the case of a loose fitting fastener. Using Analysis B, extensive sub-critical matrix damage

in the form of ply splitting was predicted at approximately 30% of the final failure load measured experimentally. This resulted in a significant reduction in the predicted bearing stiffness. The final failure prediction using Analysis B, as defined when the joint stiffness was consistently negative and/or a significant load drop, was approximately 50% of the experimentally measured value. The predicted sub-critical damage comprised splitting which evolved into extensive delamination and compressive fibre failure prior to the final failure.

These analysis results, however, were not able to match the experimentally measured non-linear bearing response accurately. This supports the conclusion of previously reported studies that highlight the importance of considering the effect of clamp-up when predicting the bearing strength of mechanically fastened joints [4]. Further studies are ongoing to overcome convergence difficulties associated with the BSAM single fastener bearing joint model that permits the consideration of clamping.

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